

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TAX SYSTEMS AND ACCOUNTING PRACTICES IN THE EU AND THE USA

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Abstract

The article is devoted to a comparative analysis of the tax systems and accounting practices in the USA and the European Union (EU) countries. It examines differences and similarities in tax structures, accounting approaches, and their impact on the economy and business environment. The influence of tax policies and accounting standards on international companies, their choice of jurisdiction, and the adaptation of business processes are analyzed. Special attention is given to aspects such as the decentralization of tax systems and the standardization of accounting practices. The article discusses the application of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in the EU and Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP) in the USA, as well as their impact on the financial reporting of multinational corporations.

Keywords: tax system, accounting, USA, European Union (EU), tax incentives, decentralization.

Introduction

Tax systems and accounting practices are crucial in economic management. With globalization and the increase in international trade, it has become crucial for multinational corporations to comprehend the variations and similarities in taxation systems and accounting standards across different regions to enhance their operations and reduce tax risks.

The importance of comparing tax systems and accounting practices in the USA and the European Union (EU) lies in the notable impact these jurisdictions have on the worldwide economy and the international business landscape, serving as a standard for numerous other countries. Having knowledge about the subtle variations in tax and accounting regulations between the USA and the EU allows for a more thorough evaluation of business risks and opportunities, as well as the

creation of strategies to reduce tax obligations and adhere to global reporting norms. The objective of this research is to conduct a detailed comparative analysis of the tax systems and accounting standards in the USA and the EU countries.

Main part. The role of the USA and the EU in the global economy

In the global economy, the USA and the EU occupy leading positions, exerting significant influence on international financial and trade processes. Both regions represent major economic blocs, accounting for a substantial share of global trade and investment. Over the past decades, there has been an active growth in international trade and mutual investments between the USA and the EU, making their economic relations increasingly integrated and interdependent (fig. 1).

Figure 1.
 Trade in goods between the EU and the USA in 2022–2023,
 billion euros, seasonally and working day adjusted [1]

Examining the tax systems and accounting standards of the world's top two economies is especially crucial in this scenario. Businesses in these markets must adjust their operations to meet different standards and laws, which may impact how they report finances and structure taxes. Comprehending these details is essential for successful planning, maximizing business efficiency, and reducing risks in the global economic setting.

Analysis of tax system features in the USA and the EU

The tax system in the USA is known for its **decentralization and multi-level setup**, which includes federal, state, and local levels. Each level possesses distinct characteristics, forming a complicated system where tax rates differ based on the state and local government.

The tax incentive and deduction system in the USA is known for its **flexibility and competitive nature**. It has a major impact on the nation's economy, offering financial support at the federal, state, and local levels. **Tax incentives and lowered** corporate tax rates have resulted in higher investment and improved competitiveness for American businesses globally. Specifically, this has led to an increase in output and employment opportunities, particularly in the high-tech and creative industries. Encouraging small and medium-sized businesses with incentives, along with providing tax credits for research and development, support the advancement of new technologies and enhance economic productivity, laying the foundation for sustained economic growth. Therefore, the tax system in the USA incorporates aspects of both encouragement and regulation, offering substantial advantages for promoting business growth and staying competitive in the global marketplace. However, the diversity of taxes and requirements at the local level creates certain challenges that may require a comprehensive approach and coordination from both businesses and federal and state governments.

Tax systems in EU nations are **varied and decentralized**, with numerous supra-national regulations and agreements focused on aligning tax structures and guaranteeing consistent regulations for participants in the single market. Despite the presence of regulations at the EU level, each individual EU member state has the authority to determine its own tax rates and systems, resulting in notable variations across countries. For instance, Germany has a comparatively high rate of corporate taxes but provides a wide array of deductions

and rewards for businesses, including those involved in research and development. France's tax system is known for imposing a heavy tax burden on both individuals and companies. The nation also enforces a social tax system, like the Contribution Sociale Généralisée, which is imposed on earnings in order to support social welfare programs. Ireland's reputation is based on its appealing low corporate tax rates, which draws many international companies to the country. It effectively leverages double taxation agreements to incentivize investment and foster a conducive business climate. Sweden and Denmark maintain high tax levels aimed at funding extensive social programs. High tax rates are offset by a developed system of social services and benefits, ensuring a high standard of living for the population and supporting economic stability [2].

The EU main objective in tax policy is to create a fair and competitive tax environment for companies and individuals, minimize tax evasion, and promote economic growth. In line with this objective, the EU is making efforts to unify indirect taxes and establish common rules regarding corporate and income taxation. Tax systems in EU countries play a crucial role in maintaining social equity and economic stability, while also significantly impacting the region's investment attractiveness and economic activity.

Therefore, the tax systems of the EU and the USA play an important role in shaping economic and social policy. Although both jurisdictions have decentralized and multi-level tax structures, their approaches to taxation and business regulation differ significantly (table 1).

Table 1.

Tax systems in EU countries and the USA [3, 4]

Category	EU countries	USA
Types of taxes	Income tax, corporate income tax, VAT, property taxes, excise taxes.	Federal income tax, corporate income tax, sales tax, payroll taxes.
Features of tax systems	Decentralization of taxes, regulation at the EU level (e.g. VAT), diversity of rates between countries, progressive taxation.	A decentralized system with taxes at the federal, regional and local levels, a wide system of tax benefits and deductions, an emphasis on stimulating business.
Impact on the economy	Provides a high level of social services, income redistribution, stimulating innovation through benefits.	Attracts investments due to low corporate tax and benefits for small businesses, stimulates economic growth and employment.
Advantages	High level of social services, support for social stability, business attraction due to low corporate taxes in some countries.	Flexibility of the tax system, business support, competitive conditions for investments, absence of income tax in some states.
Limitations	The high tax burden on individuals and businesses in a number of countries, the difficulty of adapting to different tax conditions in countries.	High variability of taxes at the state level, which complicates tax planning for companies, high tax burden on property.

According to the author, despite common features such as decentralization and multi-level structures, the tax systems of the EU and the USA have significant differences due to the unique political and economic structures of each region. Both regions present opportunities and challenges for businesses and residents. In EU countries, tax systems are more socially oriented, whereas in the USA, the emphasis is on supporting entrepreneurship and economic growth.

Analysis of accounting standards in the USA and the EU

Accounting in the USA is based on the **Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP)**, which are mandatory for all companies operating in the country. This system aims to ensure transparency, accuracy, and comparability of financial data, allowing investors, creditors, and other stakeholders to make informed decisions. The regulatory foundation for accounting in the USA is the **Financial Accounting Standards Board**

(FASB) [5]. This independent organization is in charge of developing, implementing, and revising accounting standards in the USA, taking into account global advancements and top practices. In addition to the FASB, the **Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC)** plays an important role by regulating the financial reporting of public companies and ensuring compliance with standards. The SEC is able to perform audits and inquiries in order to uphold regulations and safeguard the interests of investors. Public corporations are required to follow GAAP rules and also meet the mandates of the **Sarbanes-Oxley Act (SOX)**, which was put in place to enhance oversight of financial reporting accuracy and reliability [6]. In the USA, **there is a current implementation of digital solutions to automate accounting procedures**, which results in improved accuracy and efficiency in reporting. The accounting practices in the USA play a major role in shaping the economy by fostering transparency and accountability in companies, thereby fueling the growth of capital markets and drawing in investments.

The basis of accounting in the EU is formed by the **International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS)**, which were created by the **International Accounting Standards Board (IASB)**. The European Commission acknowledges IFRS officially and requires all companies listed on EU stock exchanges to

use them. This rule is intended to improve transparency and cohesion across the European financial market. Furthermore, EU countries can opt for national accounting standards for non-listed companies, but there is a growing move towards aligning them with IFRS to streamline business activities and draw in investors. The **European Securities and Markets Authority (ESMA)** monitors adherence to accounting standards in the EU by overseeing national regulators and promoting consistent auditing and financial reporting methods [7].

Accounting within the EU fosters economic integration and bolsters the single market by guaranteeing transparency and investor trust. The harmonization of standards fosters competition in business and lures investment, whereas domestic accounting standards consider local characteristics and promote the growth of small and medium-sized businesses.

Therefore, accounting is essential for maintaining the transparency and dependability of financial reporting, which is key for building trust among investors and driving economic growth. Accounting standards and methods vary between the EU and the USA due to their unique historical, legal, and economic features (table 2).

Table 2.

Comparative analysis of accounting in EU countries and the USA [7]

Category	EU countries	USA
The regulatory framework of accounting	IFRS for public companies, national standards for private companies.	GAAP for all companies, mandatory for public and private organizations.
Features of accounting	Unification at the EU level through IFRS, harmonization of national standards, possible differences in accounting for private companies.	Strict rules of control and regulation, mandatory GAAP compliance for all companies, SOX for public companies.
Impact on the economy	Simplifies capital raising, promotes the integration of the single market, supports small and medium-sized businesses through national standards.	Provides transparency and investor protection, attracts international investment, supports economic growth and market confidence.
Advantages	Comparability of financial statements, harmonization of standards, support for international investments.	Uniform standards, investor protection, strict control and audit through the SEC and SOX.
Limitations	Differences in national standards for private companies, the complexity of the transition to IFRS for small companies.	The high cost of compliance with standards for private companies, the difficulty of switching to GAAP for foreign companies.

A comparative analysis of accounting in the EU and the USA shows that, despite their shared goals of ensuring transparency and trust in financial reporting, these two jurisdictions employ different approaches and regulatory frameworks. The EU seeks unification and flexibility, allowing private companies to use national standards, while the USA emphasizes strict regulation and standardization to maintain reliability and transparency in reporting. These differences require multinational companies and investors to adapt and consider the specifics of each jurisdiction, which can be both an opportunity for strategic planning and a challenge in terms of regulatory compliance.

Impact of differences on international business

The differences in tax systems between the USA and EU countries significantly influence how international companies structure their operations and choose jurisdictions for their headquarters and business activities. Low corporate tax rates and favorable tax conditions in some EU countries make them attractive to multinational companies, particularly in the technology and financial sectors. These countries provide opportunities to optimize tax burdens through the structuring of holding companies and research centers. For example, **Apple** has chosen Ireland as one of its main European bases to benefit from low tax rates and a favorable corporate environment. This approach has allowed them to

optimize profit taxation and centralize their European operations in a jurisdiction with minimal tax costs [8].

In the USA, despite the relatively high tax burden at the federal level, some states do not impose corporate or income taxes, making them popular locations for registering holding companies and branches. This approach allows companies to leverage the flexibility of the American tax system to minimize tax obligations and adapt to market demands. For instance, **Tesla and Amazon** actively invest in the USA, taking advantage of the incentives for manufacturing facilities and research centers offered by specific states. Utilizing such benefits allows these companies to minimize tax obligations and create jobs, which in turn enhances their economic appeal [9].

Global corporations encounter major obstacles in creating financial reports because of the variations in accounting regulations between the EU and the USA. Businesses frequently adopt dual-reporting tactics, producing financial statements that comply with both GAAP and IFRS standards. This enables businesses to reduce the risks of not following regulations and lower the expenses linked to conforming their reports to local regulations.

Thus, the differences in tax and accounting systems between the USA and EU countries have a substantial impact on international companies, compelling them to adapt to varying standards and regulations. Multinational corporations employ various strategies and tools to optimize their operations, minimize tax liabilities, and ensure compliance with regulatory requirements in both jurisdictions.

Conclusion

The analysis shows that the tax and accounting systems in the USA and the EU significantly influence the shaping of the global economic environment, presenting both opportunities and challenges for multinational companies. Both jurisdictions have decentralized and multi-level tax structures but apply different approaches to business regulation and support. The EU focuses on harmonization and social equity, providing high social standards through progressive taxation and unified IFRS reporting principles. In contrast, the USA emphasizes entrepreneurship and innovation support through a flexible system of tax incentives and strict GAAP reporting standards.

For international businesses, the differences between these systems present both challenges and opportunities. Companies must adapt their business processes to comply with various tax and accounting requirements, necessitating the use of complex dual-reporting strategies, process automation, and the employment of qualified specialists. Understanding these

specifics and effective planning allow companies to minimize tax risks, optimize financial reporting, and successfully integrate into the international economic environment. As a result, an in-depth and comprehensive analysis of the tax and accounting systems of the world's two largest economies helps companies develop strategies aimed at their successful growth and strengthening their positions in the global market.

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